

Cite This Article: M. Santhi & P. Anitha, "Vizing's Weaker Conjecture $(\delta, \Delta) = (7, 15)$ ", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Special Issue, February, Page Number 94-100, 2017.

Abstract:

Vizing conjectured that G is a simple and Δ -critical graph with m edges then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.—In this paper—we prove the conjecture for graphs with $\delta = 7$ and $\Delta = 15$.

Key Words: Critical Graphs & Degree Sequence

1. Introduction:

Throughout this paper, $G = (V, E)$ is a graph with n vertices, m edges, maximum degree $\Delta(G)$, and a minimum degree $\delta(G)$. If $v \in V$, then $d_G(v)$ denotes the degree of a vertex v in G . Let n_j be the number of vertices of degree j in G . we use $\pi(G)$ to denote the valency list of G . Note that $n_j = 0$, then the factor j^{n_j} customary omitted $\pi(G)$. If S, T denotes the set of major and minor vertices in G respectively, and $[[S, T]]$ denotes the set of edges in G with one end in S and the other end in T . Also $[[T]]$ denotes the number of edges in T . $s(G)$ denotes the sum of degrees of minor vertices in G . Let $c(G)$ denotes the closure of G , then C denotes the Hamilton cycle of G . A well known theorem of Vizing [8] states that: if G is a simple graph with maximum degree Δ , then the edge chromatic number $X'(G)$ of G is Δ or $\Delta + 1$. A graph G is said to be of class 1 if $X'(G) = \Delta$ and it is said to be of class 2 if $X'(G) = \Delta + 1$. G is said to be (edge chromatic)critical if it is connected, class 2 and $X'(G - e) < X'(G)$ for every edge e . A critical graph G with maximum degree Δ is called Δ -critical.

Conjecture [7]: If G is a Δ -critical graph with n vertices m edges and maximum degree Δ then $m > \frac{1}{2}(n(\Delta - 1) + 3)$. Recognizing that conjecture is probably difficult to settle, Vizing remarks that he is unable to settle the simple problem.

Is it true if G is simple and Δ -critical then $m \geq \frac{\Delta^2}{2}$?

We refer this problem as the Vizing's weaker conjecture.

K. Kayathri[3] proved this conjecture for graphs with $2 \leq \delta \leq 5$.

M. Santhi [6] proved this conjecture for graphs with $\delta = 6$.

In the following results we study the structure of 15-critical graphs with $\delta = 7$ and $2m < \Delta^2$.

2. Known Results:

To prove our result, we require the following preliminary results and their consequences.

R1 [7]: Vizing's Adjacency Lemma (VAL). In a Δ -critical graph G if vw is an edge and $d(v) = k$, then w is adjacent with at least $\Delta - k + 1$ other vertices of degree Δ .

R2 [2]: A graph G with order $2s+1$ and maximum degree $2s-1$ is in class 2 iff it has size at least $2s^2 - s + 1$.

R3 [1]: A graph G with order $2s+2$ and maximum degree $2s-1$ is in class 2 iff $q(G) - \delta(G) \geq 2s^2 - s + 1$, where $q(G)$ denotes the size of G .

R4 [4]: If G has order $2s$ and maximum degree $2s-1$, then G is in class 2. If G has order $2s+1$ and maximum degree $2s$, then G is in class 2 iff the size of G is at least $2s^2 + 1$.

R5 [5]: There are no critical graphs with order $2s+2$ and maximum degree $2s$.

R6 [6]: Let G be Δ -critical graphs with $n = \Delta + 1$ or $\Delta + 2$. Then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

R7 [6]: Let G be Δ -critical graphs with $n = \Delta + 3$ and Δ odd. Then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

R8 [6]: Let G be graph with $n_\Delta \leq \Delta + 1$. If $s(G) = n_\Delta(\Delta - n_\Delta + 1) + 2k$, then $[[T]] \leq k$ and $d(v) \leq n_\Delta + k$ for all $v \in T$.

R9 [6]: Let G be graph with $n_\Delta \leq \Delta + 1$. If $s(G) = n_\Delta(\Delta - n_\Delta + 1)$ then,

i) $[[T]] = 0$

ii) $[[S, T]] = n_\Delta(\Delta - n_\Delta + 1)$ and

iii) Every vertex in S has exactly $\Delta - n_\Delta + 1$ neighbours in T .

R10 [6]: Let G be Δ -critical graphs with $n_\delta \geq n - \delta + 2$ and $s(G) = n_\Delta(\Delta - n_\Delta + 1) + 2k$. Then $[T]=k$ and $d(v) \leq n_\Delta + k$ for all $v \in T$.

R11 [6]: Let G be Δ -critical graphs with $n_\Delta = \Delta - 4$ and $2m < \Delta^2$, then

i) $5\Delta - 20 \leq s(G) < 4\Delta$.

ii) $0 \leq [T] \leq 2$ and

iii) $s(G)$ and Δ are of same parity.

R12 [3]: Let G be Δ -critical graphs with $n_\Delta = (\Delta - \delta + 2) + l$, where $l \geq 0$. If $\Delta \geq (\delta - 1 - l)(\delta - 2 - l)$, then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

If G is a Δ -critical graphs with $\delta = 7$, then by VAL $n_\Delta \geq (\Delta - \delta + 2) = \Delta - 5$.

3. Theorems:

Lemma 1:

Let G be a 15-critical graph with $\delta = 7$ and $n_\Delta = \Delta - 3$. Then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

Proof:

By R6 and R7 it is enough to verify the result when $n_\Delta = \Delta + 4$. By VAL, $n_\Delta = \Delta - \delta + 2$.

Let $n_\Delta = \Delta - \delta + 2 + l$ where $l \geq 0$. Now $n_\Delta = \Delta - 3$ and $\delta = 7$ implies that $l \geq 2$.

$$\text{When } l \geq 3, \quad (\delta - 1 - l)(\delta - 1 - l) = (6 - l)(5 - l) \\ \leq 3 \times 2 = 6 < \Delta$$

and hence by R12, $2m \geq \Delta^2$. When $l = 2$, $(\delta - 1 - l)(\delta - 1 - l) = 4 \times 2 = 8 < \Delta$ and by R7, $2m \geq \Delta^2$ if $\Delta \geq 12$.

Since $n_\Delta = \Delta - 3$, $n_\Delta \geq \Delta + 3$ and $2m \geq \Delta^2$, $n_\Delta + \delta(n - n_\Delta)$, we have

$$2m \geq (\Delta - \delta)n_\Delta + \delta n \\ \geq (\Delta - 7)(\Delta + 3) + 7(\Delta + 4) \\ \geq \Delta^2 - 3\Delta + 49 \\ \geq \Delta^2 \text{ if } \Delta \leq 16$$

Hence the result.

Lemma 2:

Let G be a Δ -critical graph with $\delta = 7$, $n_\Delta \geq \Delta + r$, $r \geq 3$. Then $2m \geq \Delta^2$ if $4\Delta \leq 28 + 7r$.

Proof:

$$2m \geq \Delta n_\Delta + 7(n - n_\Delta) \\ \geq \Delta(\Delta - 4) + 7(\Delta + r - \Delta + 4) \\ \geq \Delta^2 - 4\Delta + 28 + 7r$$

Thus, $2m \geq \Delta^2$ if $4\Delta \leq 28 + 7r$.

Lemma 3:

Let G be a 15-critical graph with $\delta = 7$, $\Delta = 15$ and $2m \geq \Delta^2$. Then

i) $n_\Delta = \Delta - 4$ and $\Delta - 5$.

ii) $n_\Delta = \Delta + r$, $r = 3, 4$

iii) $0 \leq [T] \leq 2$

iv) $s(G) = 55$ or 57 or 59 .

Proof:

i) By VAL $n_\Delta \geq \Delta - \delta + 2 \geq \Delta - 5$. Also by lemma 1, when $n_\Delta = \Delta - 4$ and $\Delta - 5$, $n_\Delta < \Delta - 3$. Hence $n_\Delta = \Delta - 4$ and $\Delta - 5$

ii) Let $n = \Delta + r$, $r = 3, 4$. By lemma 2, $2m \geq \Delta^2$ if $4\Delta \leq 28 + 7r$. Hence for 15, if $r \geq 5$ we have $2m \geq \Delta^2$. Also by R6 and R7 $2m \geq \Delta^2$ if $n = \Delta + 1$ and $\Delta + 2$.

iii) By R11, $0 \leq [T] \leq \frac{20-5}{2}$ and so $0 \leq [T] \leq 2$.

iv) By R11, $s(G)$ is odd. Also $6\Delta - 20 \leq s(G) < 4s$ and so $55 \leq s(G) < 60$.

Lemma4:

If G is a Δ -critical graph with $\Delta = 15$, $\delta = 7$, $n = \Delta + 4$ and $n_{\Delta} = \Delta - 4$ then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

Proof:

If possible let G be a Δ -critical graph with $\Delta = 15$, $\delta = 7$, $n = \Delta + 4$, $n_{\Delta} = \Delta - 4$ and $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

Then by R11, $55 \leq s(G) < 60$ and $s(G)$ is odd and so $s(G)$ is 55, 57 or 59.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now } s(G) &\geq \delta n_{\delta} + (\delta + 1)(n - n_{\Delta} - n_{\delta})\Delta \\ &\geq (\delta + 1)(n - n_{\Delta}) - n_{\delta} \end{aligned}$$

For $1 \leq n_7 \leq 4$,

$$s(G) \geq (7 + 1)(19 - 11) - 4 \geq 60, \text{ a contradiction.}$$

Now for $5 \leq n_7 \leq 8$, the possible degree sequences of G are as follows :

- i) $7^5 8^3 15^{11}$
- ii) $7^6 8^9 15^{11}$
- iii) $7^7 8 15^{11}$
- iv) $7^7 10 15^{11}$

In all the cases, we get a contradiction in the following Lemmas (Lemma 5 and Lemm 6).

Hence the Lemma.

Lemma 5:

If G is a Δ -critical graph with $\Delta = 15$, $\delta = 7$, $n = \Delta + 4$, $n_{\Delta} = \Delta + 4$, $s(G) = 57$, then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

Proof:

Assume the contrary that $2m < \Delta^2$. Then the only possible degree sequence is

$$\pi(G) = 7^7 8 15^{11}, \text{ given in Lemma 4. But by } |[T]| \leq 1. \text{ But by VAL, } |[T]| = 0.$$

Now, $|[S, T]| = 57$ if $|[T]| = 0$.

Then in G , one of the following two cases arises:

- i) $|[T]| = 0$, two major vertices have 6 minor neighbours and 9 major vertices have 5 minor neighbours.
- ii) $|[T]| = 0$, one major vertex has 7 minor neighbours and 10 major vertices have 5 minor neighbours.

$$\text{Now } \pi(G) = 7^7 8 15^{11}.$$

Let v_1 be a vertex of degree 7.

Let D be a subset of $T \setminus \{v_1\}$ with $|D| = 7$.

Let $D' = T/D$. Then $|D'| = 1$ and $v_1 \in D'$.

Let $D = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6, u_7\}$ and $D' = \{v_1\}$

We shall fix the degrees of u_i 's and v_i 's accordingly.

Let $G_1 = G/D$. Now $|v(G_1)| = 13$. Then $\Delta(G_1) \leq 12$.

The number of vertices of degree is in G_1 . Since we have deleted 6 vertices from G and $\Delta(G) = 15$, the major vertices in G are of degree ≥ 9 in G_1 .

$$\text{Hence } n'_8 + n'_9 + n'_{10} + n'_{11} + n'_{12} \geq n_{\Delta}(G) = 11$$

$$|V_1| = n'_8 + n'_9 + n'_{10} + n'_{11} + n'_{12} \geq n_{\Delta}(G) = 11$$

Moreover $v_1 \in G_1$ and $d_{G_1}(v_1) = 7$.

Let $v_1 = \{v \in V(G_1) : d_{G_1}(v) \geq 8\}$ and

$$v_2 = \{v \in V(G_1) : d_{G_1}(v) < 8\}.$$

Then $|V_1| = n'_8 + n'_9 + n'_{10} + n'_{11} + n'_{12} \geq n_{\Delta}(G) = 11$.

Let $v \in V_1$. Now for all $w \in V(G_1)$

$$d_{G_1}(v) + d_{G_1}(w) \geq 8 + 6 = 14 \geq |V(G_1)|.$$

So in the closure of $c(G_1)$, every $v \in V_1$ is adjacent with every other vertex in G_1 . Moreover for all $u \in V_2$,

$$d_{C(G_1)}(u) \geq |V_1| \geq n_\Delta(G) = 1.$$

So, for every pair of vertices u and w in V_2 , $d_{C(G_1)}(u) + d_{C(G_1)}(w) \geq 11 + 11 = 22 > |V(G_1)|$

So, $c(G_1)$ is complete and hence G_1 is Hamiltonian.

Let C be a Hamiltonian cycle of G_1 .

Let $G' = G/E(C)$.

Since G is of class 2, G' is also of class 2.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{Also } d_{G'}(u) &= d_G(u) \text{ for } u \in D \text{ and} \\ d_{G'}(v) &= d_G(v) - 2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

In particular $d_{G'}(v_1) = 5$ and so $\delta(G_1) = 5$. Also $\Delta(G') = \Delta(G) - 2 = 13$

Let H be a 13-critical subgraph of G' .

Let h_i'' denote the number of vertices of degree i in H .

Let S', T' respectively denote the set of major and minor vertices in H .

We have $|S'| \leq n_\Delta(G) = 11$. By VAL, $n_\Delta \geq \Delta - S + 2$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have } \delta(H) &\geq \Delta(H) - |S'| + 2 \\ &\geq 13 - 11 + 2 \\ &\geq 4 \end{aligned}$$

$\delta(H) = 5$

Now $|S'| = 11$. Note that $d_H(v_i) = 5$ and so v_1 has 5 major neighbourhood in cases (i) and (ii)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{Then in (i), } |[S', T']| &\leq (5 \times 4) + (4 \times 5) + (2 \times 6) = 52 \\ \text{in (ii), } |[S', T']| &\leq (5 \times 4) + (5 \times 5) + (1 \times 7) = 52 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

Since $\delta(H) = 5$, it follows that $H = G'/E_1$,

where $E_1 \subseteq [T]_{G'}$, and no edge in E_1 is incident with vertices of degree 13 or 4. While removing C from G , we have removed only two edges from $[T, S]$ (two edges incident with one minor vertex in D).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{So } s(G') &= s(G) - (1 \times 2) \\ &= 57 - 2 = 55 \end{aligned}$$

Then $s(H) \geq s(G') - 2|E_1|$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } |[S', T']| &= s(H) - 2|[T']| \\ &= 55 - 2(|E_1| + |[T']|) \\ &\geq 55 - 2 \geq 53 \quad \text{contradicting (2)} \end{aligned}$$

$\delta(H) \geq 6$

Now $n_5(H) = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} n_5(H) = 0 &\Rightarrow H \subseteq G'/v_1 && \text{(where } d(v_1) = 5) \\ &\Rightarrow |S'| \leq 11 - 4 = 7 && \text{(since } v_1 \text{ has at least 4 major neighbours in } G') \\ &\Rightarrow \delta(H) \geq 8 && \text{(using VAL)} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Let u_1 be a vertex of degree 7 that has only major neighbours in G .

Then $d_{G'}(u_1) = 7$

Now by (3), $\delta(H) \geq 8$

$$\delta(H) \geq 8 \Rightarrow H \subseteq G'/u_1$$

$$\Rightarrow |S'| \leq 11 - 7 = 4$$

$$\Rightarrow 11$$

We note that $n_{10} + n_{11} = 0$ in G .

$$\text{Hence } n_8'' + n_9'' \leq n_{10} + n_{11} + n_{12} + n_{13} + n_{14} + n_{15} = 11$$

So, $|V(H)| \leq 11$ is a contradiction.

This completes the proof.

Lemma 6:

If G is an Δ -critical graph with $\Delta = 15, \delta = 7, n = \Delta + 4, n_\Delta = \Delta - 4$ and $s(G) = 59$, then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

Proof:

Assume the contrary that $2m < \Delta^2$. Then the possible degree sequences are

$$\text{i) } 7^5 8^3 15^{11}$$

$$\text{ii) } 7^6 8^9 15^{11}$$

$$\text{iii) } 7^7 10 15^{11} \text{ given in lemma 4.}$$

By **R[8]**, $|[T]| \leq 2$. But by **VAL**, $|[T]| \leq 1$

$$\text{Now } |[S, T]| = \begin{cases} 59, & \text{if } |[T]| = 0 \\ 57, & \text{if } |[T]| = 1 \end{cases}$$

Then in G , one of the following five cases arises:

i) $|[T]| = 0$, four major vertices have 6 minor neighbours and seven major vertices have 5 minor neighbours.

ii) $|[T]| = 0$, two major vertices have 6 minor neighbours and one major vertex have seven minor neighbours and 8 major vertices have 5 minor neighbours.

iii) $|[T]| = 0$, two major vertices have 7 minor neighbours and nine major vertices have 5 minor neighbours.

iv) $|[T]| = 1$, two major vertices have 6 minor neighbours and nine major vertices have 5 minor neighbours.

v) $|[T]| = 0$, one major vertex has 7 minor neighbours and two major vertices have 5 minor neighbours and 8 major vertices have 5 minor neighbours.

Also $d(v) \leq n_\Delta + 1 = 12$ for all $v \in T$.

$$\text{Let } \pi(G) = \begin{cases} 7^5 8^3 15^{11} \\ 7^6 8^9 15^{11} \\ 7^7 10 15^{11} \end{cases}$$

Let v_1 be a vertex of degree 7.

Let D be a subset of $T/\{v_1\}$ with $|D| = 6$.

Let $D' = T/D$. Then $|D'| = 2$ and $v_1 \in D'$.

Let $D = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6\}$ and $D' = \{v_1, v_2\}$.

We shall fix the degree of u_i 's, v_i 's accordingly.

Let $G_1 = G/D$.

Now $|V(G_1)| = 13$. Then $\Delta(G_1) \leq 12$.

Since $\delta(G) = 7$ and $|[T]| \leq 1$, we have $\delta(G_1) = 6$.

Let $V_1 = \{v \in V(G_1) : d_{G_1}(v) \geq 9\}$,

$V_2 = \{v \in V(G_1) : d_{G_1}(v) < 9\}$.

As in lemma 6, we can check that G_1 is hamiltonian.

Let c be a hamiltonian cycle of G_1 .

Let $G' = G/E(C)$.

Since G is of class 2, G' is of class 2.

Let S', T' be defined as in lemma 6.

Then $|S'| \leq 11$ and $\delta(H) \geq 4$.

$\delta(H) = 5$

Now $|S'| = 11$

Then $V(H) = V(G')$ and $d_H(v_1) = 5$..

Now we consider the cases (i) to (v).

Note that $d_H(v_1) = 5$. And so in H , V_1 has 4 major neighbourhood in case (i) and (iii) and has at least 3 major neighbourhood in cases (iv) and (v).

Then in (i) $|[S', T']| \leq (4 \times 3) + (4 \times 6) + (3 \times 5) = 51$.

(ii) $|[S', T']| \leq (4 \times 3) + (2 \times 6) + (1 \times 7) + (4 \times 5) = 51$,

(iii) $|[S', T']| \leq (4 \times 3) + (2 \times 7) + (5 \times 5) = 51$,

(iv) $|[S', T']| \leq (3 \times 3) + (2 \times 6) + (6 \times 5) = 51$,

(v) $|[S', T']| \leq (3 \times 3) + (1 \times 7) + (7 \times 5) = 51$.

(1)

But in all cases,

$$s(G') = s(G) - (2 \times 2)$$

$$= 59 - 4 = 55$$

Also $\delta(H) = 5$ and so $H = G'/E_1$, where $E_1 \subseteq [T]_{G'}$, and no edge in E_1 is incident with vertices of degree 13 or 5 (Then $|E_1| \leq 1$).

Now in $|[T']| + |E_1| = |[T]_{G'}| \leq 1$

Then $s(H) = s(G') - 2|E_1|$

$$= 55 - 2|E_1|$$

Now in (i) – (iii), $H = G'$ and $|[T', S']| = 55$

In (iv) and (v) $|[T', S']| \geq 55 - 2 = 53$ contradicting to (1)

$\delta(H) \geq 6$

Then $H \subseteq G'/v_1$ where $d(v_1) = 5$

Now $n_5(H) = 0 \Rightarrow |S'| \leq 11 - 3 = 8$ (since v_1 has at least 3 major neighbours in G).

$$\Rightarrow \delta(H) \geq 7 \text{ (using VAL)}$$

Now we have three possible degree sequences:

i) $7^6 8^9 15^{11}$

ii) $7^5 8^4 5^{11}$

iii) $7^7 10 15^{11}$

$$\text{Let } d(v_2) = \begin{cases} 8 & \text{in (i) and (ii)} \\ 10 & \text{in (iii)} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Then } d_{G'}(v_2) = \begin{cases} 6 & \text{in (i) and (ii)} \\ 8 & \text{in (iii)} \end{cases}$$

Also by VAL, v_2 has at most one minor neighbours in G .

$$\delta(H) \geq 7 \Rightarrow H \subseteq G'/v_2$$

$$\Rightarrow |S'| \leq \begin{cases} 11-5 & \text{in (i) and (ii)} \\ 11-7 & \text{in (iii)} \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow |S'| \leq \begin{cases} 6 & \text{in (i) and (ii)} \\ 4 & \text{in (iii)} \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \delta(H) \geq \begin{cases} 9 & \text{in (i) and (ii)} \\ 11 & \text{in (iii)} \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow |\delta(H)| \leq 11, \text{ a contradiction.}$$

This completes the proof.

Theorem 1:

If G is a 15-critical graph with $\delta = 7$ and $n_\Delta = \Delta - 4$, then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

Proof:

By Lemma 5 and Lemma 6, we get the result.

Theorem 2:

If G is a 15-critical graph with $\delta = 7$ and $n_\Delta = \Delta - 5$, then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

Proof:

By R11, $55 \leq s(G) < 60$ and $s(G)$ is odd and so $s(G)$ is 55 or 57 or 59.

Since $n_\Delta = (\Delta - 5, n_\Delta = 11)$ is odd and also $s(G)$ is odd, in the possible degree sequences the number of odd vertices is odd. It is impossible.

Hence the theorem.

Proof of the Main Theorem:

Theorem 3:

If G is a 15-critical graph with $\delta = 7$ then $2m \geq \Delta^2$.

Proof:

By VAL, $n_\Delta \geq \Delta - 5 + 2 \geq \Delta - 5$.

By R6, R7 and lemma 1, it is enough to verify the result when $n_{\Delta+4} \geq \Delta + 4$ and $n_\Delta = \Delta - 4$ and $\Delta - 5$.

By Theorem 1 and 2, the main theorem follows.

References:

1. G. Chetwynd and A. J. W. Hilton: "The chromatic index of even order with many edges", j.Graph theory 8(1984), 463-470.
2. G. Chetwynd and A. J. W. Hilton: "Partial edge – Colourings of graphs which are nearly complete", Graph Theory and combinatorics (Ed.B.Ballobas), Academic press, London (1984), 81-97.
3. K. Kayathri: "Chromatic numbers of Graphs", Ph.D., Thesis, Madurai Kamaraj University (1996)
4. M. Plantholt: "The Chromatic index of Graph with a spanning star", J.Graph Theory 5 (1981, 5-13)
5. M. Plantholt: "The Chromatic index of Graph with large maximum degree", Discrete Math, 47 (1983), 91-96.
6. M. Santhi: "Coloring of Graphs", Ph.D., Thesis, Madurai Kamaraj University (2008)
7. V. G. Vizing: "Critical graphs with given chromatic class" (Russian), Diskret – Analiz, 5 (1965) 9-17.
8. V. G. Vizing: "Some unsolved problems in Graph Theory", Uaspekhi Mat, Nauk 23 (1968) 117-134, Russian math. Surveys 23 (1968) 125-142